

Promotion, Renumeration and Teachers Productivity: Evidence from Nasarawa State

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Abstract

In this study, promotion, renumeration and teachers' productivity: evidence from Nasarawa state was investigated. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the influence of teachers' salaries and promotion on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools. The study employed descriptive survey design in gathering data. Questionnaire on Teacher Motivation and Students' Academic Achievement (QOTMASAA) was used as instrument for data collection. The sample comprised 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students drawn from 26 public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. The data collected were analysed using Frequency count and simple percentages in answering the research questions while chi-square statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that salaries and promotion of teachers are motivation strategy that enhance teaching and impact on students' achievement in Nasarawa state. It was therefore recommended among others that teacher salary scale should be augmented by the Government and at the same time, the government should ensure that promotion exercises for teachers are done on time.

Keywords: Teacher productivity, Promotion, Renumeration.

Introduction

The performance of students in Mathematics and English Language has raised serious concern to stakeholders in the education sector. Mathematics and English Language been a core subject requires students to attain at least a credit grade point either in placement or certification examinations. As has reviewed from literature (Muhammad & Sabeen, 2011), the quality of education in Nigeria for more than

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three decades has fallen due to factors such as poor instructional materials, inadequate educational resources, poor school environment, incompetent teachers and poor teachers' motivation. Motivation according to Akoju (2005) is used to describe those processes, both initiative and rational by which people seek to satisfy the basic drives, perceived needs and personal goals, which trigger off human behaviour. Odoh (2015) asserts that motivation is the willingness to exert high levels of efforts towards organizational goals conditioned by the efforts ability to satisfy some individual needs. In other words, motivation is a management function that stimulates individuals to accomplish laid down institutional goals. Lautham (2008) opined that teachers' motivation are efforts geared towards the improvement of the teaching-learning situation to the benefits of both the teachers and learners; through adequate supervisions in the identified areas of academic needs. Sogomo (2013) identified some crucial components teacher motivation to include the following: wages and salaries, promotion of teachers, working environment and training and retraining of teachers.

Teacher promotion is the advancement of a teacher within a school position or job task. Teacher promotion may be the result of a teacher's proactive pursuit of a higher ranking or as a reward by for good performance. Typically is usually associated with a higher rate of pay or financial bonus. Teacher promotion may also refer to the transition of a teacher to a new position which commands higher pay, privileges or status compared with the old. It is a vertical move in rank and responsibility. The goal of any school is to attain improved performance of its learners, but this may ever be achieved if the promotion of its teachers is not given the required attention. The advancement of teachers through promotion is an issue that cannot be relegated to the background (Strauss and Sayles, 2006). If the school aims at attaining improved academic performance. Promotion motivates teachers and may sometimes contribute towards advancing their level of commitment in the classroom.

Salaries are the remuneration paid or payable to teachers for work performed on behalf for services provided. Normally, an employer is not permitted to withhold the wages or any part thereof, except as permitted or required by law. In Nigeria, they are usually paid on monthly basis. Wages and salaries may also refer to the price paid for services rendered over time (Kumar, 2019). When paid promptly, wages and salaries could provide effective motivation for the teacher to work thereby improving their job performance. Furthermore, an improvement in teachers' job performance through motivation may likely enhance students' academic performance in school. On the other hand, failure or refusal to motivate teachers may probably reduce their work rate and this could lead to a drop in performance rate and low academic performance. Aside prompt payment of staff wages and salaries, the promotion of teachers is another important index for teacher motivation.

Regular promotion of teachers enhances their work performance within the school because regular promotion motivates them to work effectively and efficiently thereby enhancing their commitment level in classroom instruction in such a way that enables learners attain high academic achievement. Giving little or no attention to the promotion of teachers could dampen their job thereby leading to a decline in job

performance in the classroom and this could have a negative impact on students' academic achievement. The aim of learning in the school system is to ensure a permanent change in behaviour of learners which is exhibited not only in their attitude or interest, but also in their academic achievement as reflected by their grades in school. A critical review of the academic achievement of senior secondary school students of Nasarawa show that the trend in academic achievement in core subjects has not been encouraging. This is why the issue of teacher motivation cannot be relegated to the background.

In most cases, a well-motivated teacher, who earns a substantial salary, receives regular promotion, works in a conducive learning environment and undergoes regular training and retraining is may likely be dedicated to his/ her teaching so as to bring about the needed learning on the part of students. It is therefore the duty of a teacher to get the students to do what they are expected to do in order to help the educational system achieve its goal (Usman, 2015). Similarly, Gibson (2013) posited that educational goals can be accomplished by giving teachers adequate motivation, the necessary attention and priority they deserve while they are working towards achieving the purpose of learning. One of the cardinal reasons for working in life is to satisfy the basic human needs. Ojewole (2014) observed that under normal circumstances, individuals choose those occupations which they feel can meet some of their peculiar needs in life. Teachers usually complain of lack of motivational incentives for them. Accordingly, Etuk (2012) buttressed that teachers often complain of lack of fringe benefits of the workers like transport, housing, and medical allowances; lack of payment of leave allowances for many years; lack of recognition, merits awards, bonus and in-service training.

It is believed that if teachers' pay, working conditions and fringe benefits given to the teachers are judged to be good by the teachers, they will put more effort at work. In other words, they will prepare adequately for their lesson, go to school regularly and punctually, attending classes as schedule teach the students well, give and mark assignments, test and examination. To this end, this study aims to investigate promotion, remuneration and teachers' productivity: evidence from Nasarawa state.

Theoretical Framework

McGregor's Motivation Theory

Maslow hypothesized that human behaviour is motivated by a number of competing needs (need for self-actualization, aesthetic need, self-esteem needs, social needs, security/safety need and physiological needs) that can be arranged in a hierarchy respectively. Maslow argued that the accomplishment of these needs brings about survival and enhance the person's psychological functioning.

In this scenario, one can say that the above needs are undoubtedly relevant for teachers' survival and psychological functioning which are indispensable in helping the student learn appropriately. If such needs are pursued for the teacher, it will surely motivate him to work devotedly towards realizing educational goals of our dear society.

McGregor's motivation theory is relevant to teachers' productivity in the school system. This is because motivation in the school system encompasses forces both within (internal) and external to the individual worker. In this situation, the favourability of the aforementioned elements to the teacher will go a long way in influencing his commitment to the teaching-learning endeavour.

Research Objectives

The study is aimed at investigating promotion, remuneration and teachers' productivity: evidence from Nasarawa state. Specifically, the study intends to:

The study specifically intends to:

1. Ascertain the influence of teachers' salaries on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.
2. Determine the influence of teachers' promotion on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa state public senior secondary schools.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the influence of teachers' salaries on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?
2. What is the influence of teachers' promotion on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: Teachers' salaries have no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

HO₂: Teachers' promotion has no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Research Methods

This study adopted descriptive survey design. This design is considered appropriate because the study involves collection of data from a representative sample of the population within a short period of time.

Nworgu (2006) opined that descriptive design aims at collecting data on, and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. A sample of 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students was selected for the study. Cluster sampling technique was used to draw the sample for the study. During the process, each local government area of the state was treated as clusters, using simple random sampling. In the process five local government areas were drawn by balloting with replacement. Furthermore, 26 schools were selected across the five selected local government areas using simple random sampling. In all, 26 schools 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students were selected for the study. The study used questionnaire tagged Questionnaire on Teacher Motivation and Students' Academic Achievement (QOTMASAA). The data collected were analysed using Frequency count and simple percentages in answering the research questions while chi-square statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Questions 1: What is the influence of teachers' salaries on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Table1. Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Respondents Ratings on the Influence of Teachers' Salaries among Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Teachers' Salaries	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	Remark
I teach better when my salaries are paid and this enhances students' academic performance.	38	58	40	115	2.94	1.13	Accepted
I get discouraged when salaries and allowances are delayed and this explains why my students cannot perform better	25	55	57	112	3.03	1.04	Accepted
I am paid my full salaries and this encourages me to teach better to improve students' academic performance	50	61	62	76	2.66	1.11	Accepted
I am owed salaries for several months and this explains why students' academic performance have not improved.	79	70	9	94	2.49	1.27	Accepted
My salary arrears are paid regularly and this makes my teaching effective thereby enhancing students' academic performance.	17	23	68	141	3.34	.906	Accepted

My salaries are improved annually and this explains why I teach better to improve students' academic performance.	96	67	36	50	2.16	1.15	Accepted
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviations					2.77	1.10	

Table 1 show that the mean ratings of items on teachers' salaries on students' academic achievement. The mean ratings are of item 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 are above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating that teachers accepted these items. This means that the respondents agreed that teachers' salary influences the academic achievement of students' in Nasarawa state.

Research Questions 2: What is the influence of teachers' promotion on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Table 2. Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Respondents Ratings on the Influence of Teachers' Promotion among Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Teachers' Promotion	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	Remark
I get promoted when due and this enhanced my zeal to work towards improving students' academic performance.	61	51	38	99	2.70	1.23	Accepted
The prolonged delay in promotion has made my teaching ineffective and this hampers students' academic performance	5	48	42	154	3.39	.864	Accepted
I get excited each time I am promoted because it encourages me to teach students to perform better	54	27	69	99	2.86	1.17	Accepted
I have been on salary grade level for a long time and this shows why my teaching has not enhanced students' academic performance.	83	71	26	69	2.33	1,20	Accepted
Promotion arrears are implemented as when due and this enhance productivity	39	34	46	130	3.07	1.13	Accepted
I am owed promotion arrears and this explains why students cannot learn from effectively from me to perform better.	56	24	47	122	2.94	1.22	Accepted
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviations					2,88	1.14	

Table 2 show that the mean ratings of items on teachers' promotion on students' academic achievement. The mean ratings are of item 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6 are above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating that teachers accepted these items. This means that the respondents agreed that teachers' promotion influences the academic achievement of students' in Nasarawa state.

Testing of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Hypothesis 1 (HO₁): Teachers' salaries have no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Table 3. Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Teachers' Salaries on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Variables	\bar{X}	Std.D	df	Alpha (α)	χ^2 cal	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Salaries*	16.61	2.88	248	0.05	488.92	.011	Reject H ₀₁
Academic Ach.	60.49	5.71					

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows a significant influence; Ach = Achievement

Table 3 above shows the Chi-square test statistics (χ^2) on the influence of teachers' salaries on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. The result reveals that there is a significant influence of teachers' salaries on academic achievement of secondary school students given at; [N = 249, $\chi^2 = 488.92$, $p < .05$]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2 (HO₂): Teachers' promotion has no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Table 4. Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Teachers' Promotion on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Variables	\bar{X}	Std.D	df	Alpha (α)	χ^2 cal	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Promotion*	17.29	3.22	248	0.05	394.86	.450	Accept
Academic Ach.	60.49	5.71					H ₀₂

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows a significant influence; Ach = Achievement

Table 4 above shows the Chi-square test statistics (χ^2) on the influence of teachers' promotion on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. The result reveals that there is no significant influence of teachers' promotion on academic achievement of secondary school students given at; [N = 249, $\chi^2 = 394.86$, $p < .05$]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study on hypothesis one reveal that there is a significant influence of teachers' salaries on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Finding from this study is in line with study by Nyakundi, Raburu, and Okwara (2019) who concluded that the teacher motivation had a significant influence to academic performance of students. Emeya and Antiaobong (2016) result revealed that motivation and regular payment of salary jointly contributes to Agricultural Science teachers' commitment in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. This is further supported by the study of Uwannah, Eteete and Mark (2019) findings which revealed a significant combined contribution of work environment and compensation on teachers' productivity, a significant relative contribution of compensation to teachers' productivity but a non-significant relative contribution of work environment to teachers' productivity. In the same direction with the findings of this study is Garba and Mohammed (2016) result's which shows that there is significant relationship between motivation of teachers and academic performance of Secondary School Students. Result of the study by Adeyemo, Oladipupo and Omisore (2019) revealed that majority of the teachers are not satisfied with their condition of service. Three quarter of teachers studied are not satisfied with the fringe benefits attached to their salaries while majority of the respondents are not satisfied with the condition of service of teachers. The findings of this study are corroborated by Babagana and Babagana (2015) findings on establishing the relationship between staff remuneration and performance of Ramat polytechnic Maiduguri students revealed a strong and positive relationship between staff remuneration and students' performance. Ehineni (2017) findings showed that teachers' morale made significant contribution to the prediction of students' academic performance. It accounted for 58.9% of the total variance in students' academic performance. In the same vein, all the indices of teachers' morale individually made significant contribution to the prediction of students' academic performance, with teachers' salary as the best predictor.

The result on hypothesis two reveals that there is no significant influence of teachers' promotion on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Kihara, Kimiti and Muola (2018) study established that teachers' appreciation through rewards and incentives for good performance enhances work commitment, increases engagement with students consequently leading to improved academic performance. Ofojebe and Ezugoh (2010) reveals those motivational strategies like staff training and development, promotion, salary, remuneration, working conditions, status and participatory decision making, acted as a barrier towards achieving quality assurance in the educational system. Further in line with the findings of this study, Ekabu, Nyagah and Kalai (2018) results showed that promotional prospects have a negative and an inverse relationship with turnover intention. The results also showed a significant relationship between promotion prospects and turnover intentions of secondary school teachers in Meru County. The results concluded that teachers' motivation in secondary schools in Meru County is low with

teachers having poor morale and low levels of commitment to their job due to lack of promotion and stagnation in one grade hence high turnover intentions set in.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is pertinent to note that salaries and promotion of teachers have a significant impact on students' achievement in Nasarawa state. It was therefore recommended among others that teacher salary scale should be augmented by the Government. Teachers should be adequately motivated through good salary structures, financial loans, grants, awards for excellence and other compensation packages to embrace both financial and non-financial rewards that will boost their morale and commitment to duty. Government should not pay deaf ears to teachers' motivational needs especially in such areas like good salaries or remuneration. Additionally, the government should ensure that promotion exercises for teachers are done on time. This will boost the morale of the teachers which will also lead to greater input in the job and a better output for the students.

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